

READ ME

Please follow the below instructions to download and operate the non-targeted method and data processing program described in the manuscript.

1. Go to <https://thermo.flexnetoperations.com/>, register and download Compound Discoverer version 2.1. Install as per manufacturers instructions.

2. Download Python, including the modules 'Pandas', 'Numpy', 'Openpyxl' and 'xlrd'. Note: use xlrd version 1.2.0. The modules can be installed on a Windows PC in the command prompt using the following commands, 'pip install Pandas', 'pip install Numpy', 'pip install Openpyxl' and 'pip install xlrd==1.2.0'.

3. Download all manuscript data files in the repository (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4701800) and save in the same folder with no sub-directories.

4. Open Compound Discoverer, select 'New Study and Analysis'. Enter the 'Study Name and Directory Structure', leave the 'workflow' empty (displays as 'empty workflow'), then press 'Next'.

5. Select the raw negative **OR** positive ionisation data files for analysis, then press 'Next'. Negative and positive data files are analysed separately using two different Compound Discoverer methods.

6. Label each raw file as 'Blank' or 'Sample' in the 'Sample Type' column. Then click 'Next'.

7. Under 'Study Variable' select 'Sample Type' and press 'Next', then 'Finish'.

6. Navigate to 'Libraries' at the top of the page and select 'Mass Lists & Spectral Databases'. Select 'Add Files' and then select the following files download from the repository:

'NegativeESI_mzVaultLibrary'

'PositiveESI_[M+H]+mzVaultLibrary'

'PositiveESI_[M+Na]+mzVaultLibrary'

Then close the Mass Lists & Spectral Databases' window.

7. Navigate to 'Workflows' and select the tab 'open'. Choose the respective method for 'AmbientPM' or 'SurfaceWaters' depending on the application (the difference between these methods are described in the manuscript) and either the negative **OR** positive ESI method depending on the ionisation polarity of the raw data files.

8. In the 'Workflow Tree' window, scroll down and click on 'Search mzVault'. On the left under '1. Search Settings', 'mzVault Library', open and select the respective negative **OR** positive mzVault Library, then click save in the workflow window. Note: this will only need to be performed once and for each ionisation mode, selecting for positive **both** [M+H]⁺ and [M+Na]⁺ libraries.

9. In the right-hand 'Analysis' window, select 'Run'.

10. Once the analysis has completed, right click under the 'Compounds' tab, select 'Export', then 'Export to Excel'. In the pop-up box, select for 'Level 1' 'Compounds', 'Level 2' 'Compounds per File', 'Level 3' 'Features'. In 'Path' select where the exported data should be saved and provide a file name.

11. Go to the depository folder and double-click 'processor.py'. The Python data processing program will then open.

12. Under 'Input Files' select the exported Compound Discoverer Excel File. The program will describe its state at the bottom of the window (e.g. 'Idle').

13. Compound Discoverer labels each data file with 'F' followed by a number (see the 'Input Files' tab in Compound Discoverer). Note which data files are blanks and samples. Then in the Python processor program, select the blank files (using the CTRL key to select multiple data files).

14. Select under 'Ions for Normalisation' $[M-H]^-$ or $[M+H]^+$.

15. Cut-off ratios can be changed as required, along with the blank removal parameters (i.e. the parameters used to detect blank artefacts and remove them from the sample data). The recommended blank removal parameters are reported in the manuscript.

15. Finally, click 'Chose Output File', provide the path and a file name to save the processed data, and click 'Start Processing'.

Processed Data Notes:

The 'Found Blanks' sheet displays the compounds detected in the blanks that were removed from the sample data files, specifying which data files they were removed from.

The 'Compound Composition Counts' sheet reports the number of compounds detected in each sample by the elements in their molecular formula, i.e. contain **only** CHO, CHON *etc.*

The 'Chemical Groupings CHO', '..... CHON', '.....CHOS', '.....CHONS' sheets provide in columns A to H the relative sample peak areas of the detected compounds, grouped by their elemental composition and number of carbon atoms in each molecular formula (as shown in Figure 2 of the manuscript). The relative sample peak areas of the detected compounds are also **separately** calculated (see columns I to P) using the dissolved organic matter (DOM) chemical groupings and elemental composition (described in the manuscript).